

Personal Legacy Motivation as A Psychological Mechanism for Increasing Climate Action and Coping with Climate Change Stressors

Stylios Syropoulos,^{1,2*} Andrea Mah,² and Ezra Markowitz^{1,2}

1. Department of Psychology and Neuroscience, Boston College, Boston, Massachusetts, United States
2. The Schiller Institute for Integrated Science and Society, Boston, Massachusetts, United States
3. Department of Psychological and Brain Sciences, University of Massachusetts Amherst, Amherst, Massachusetts, United States
4. Ezra Markowitz, Department of Environmental Conservation, University of Massachusetts Amherst, Amherst, Massachusetts, United States

ABSTRACT

Climate change requires transformational changes to the ways we relate to one another and our planet, produce and consume resources, and live our lives, both as individuals and collectively. However, engaging in meaningful individual and societal change while facing existential threat is deeply challenging and can feel stressful, hopeless, and overwhelming, making it all too easy to ignore and turn away from. In this commentary, we argue that the concepts of personal legacy motivation and generativity hold underappreciated potential for promoting positive mental health outcomes in the context of climate change, particularly through their capacity to promote active coping with the issue. We describe the ways that these concepts could help individuals withstand the mental health impacts of climate change and conclude by offering important future directions for empirical tests of how personal legacy and generativity could be utilized as tools to promote adaptive coping with the different psychological stressors posed by climate change.

Keywords: *Personal legacy; Generativity; Coping; Mental health; Climate change*

*Correspondence: syropoul@bc.edu

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PERSPECTIVE

The Threat of Climate Change

The past decade has witnessed a much-needed increase in attention to and concern for the mental health impacts of climate change (Coffey et al., 2021; Doherty & Clayton, 2011). This newfound attention is justified: global polling has found that most people see climate change as one of the most important threats facing humankind (Atske, 2022; The Global Risks Report 2022, 17th Edition, 2022). In the U.S., recent polling found that a robust majority of Americans were worried about climate change (Leiserowitz et al., 2023). Given the many pathways through which climate change can directly and indirectly harm mental health, this rise in public concern is not surprising (Doherty & Clayton, 2011; Mah et al., 2020).

There is also some evidence that the idea of climate change itself can be stressful, for example through news about climate disasters (Berry et al., 2010). New measures capture climate change-specific emotions such as climate change anxiety (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020), eco-anger, eco-anxiety, and eco-depression (Stanley et al., 2021). Using these and other measures, researchers have found that people are emotionally responding to climate change in ways that could negatively impact their mental health (Feather & Williams, 2022; Latkin et al., 2022; Stanley et al., 2021). For example, people who expressed greater worry about climate change also reported higher levels of climate change anxiety (i.e., cognitive-emotional and functional impairment associated with thoughts about climate change; Feather & Williams, 2022).

Although there are concerns that the harmful psychological impacts of climate change may hinder successful coping, it is crucial to recognize that coping focused on these psychological impacts alone is not enough. It is imperative that individuals engage in behaviors that will aid in mitigating or adapting to climate change (Doherty & Clayton, 2011). Climate change is a legitimate threat to our well-being, and anxiety or fear plays a critical role in motivating necessary protective actions to address this threat. As experts have argued, there is likely an optimal level of climate change concern that can effectively prompt pro-environmental action without paralyzing individuals (Feather & Williams, 2022). Interestingly, climate change distress has been found to positively correlate with engagement in activism, even after controlling for depression and anxiety (Latkin et al., 2022). Consequently, it is a challenge for psychologists to understand how to balance the need for mental health protection with the necessity of collective action on climate change.

Two Key Psychological Mechanisms: Personal Legacy Motivation and Generativity

Here, we propose that the related but distinct psychological mechanisms of personal legacy motivation and generativity can be effectively leveraged to motivate climate action while simultaneously mitigating some of the potential mental health impacts caused by climate change. The concept of personal legacy has been defined as “an enduring meaning attached to one's identity and manifested in the impact that one has on others beyond the temporal constraints of the lifespan” (Wade-Benzoni, 2019). Building on this definition, legacy motivation (i.e., seeking to build a legacy) refers to a person's attempts and effort to create an enduring identity based on the way they impact others. Scholars have explored this topic by examining people's concern for their personal legacy (i.e., their legacy motivation) and their generative disposition (i.e., generativity). Generativity refers to a person's propensity and willingness to engage in acts that promote the well-being of younger generations, often as a means of increasing the long-term survival of the species (Flett, 2018). Although generativity and legacy motivation are distinguishable, they share similarities regarding intergenerational scope. Both

constructs involve a focusing of one's attention towards the impact and beneficence they can bestow on others, whether they are kin or not.

In the sections that follow, we argue that people's legacy motivation and generative disposition could prove to be useful tools for motivating pro-environmental action. We highlight correlational and experimental research which supports this link. We then briefly review research that suggests that generativity and legacy can benefit people's mental health. Considering these two lines of evidence, we then theorize that both wanting to leave legacy and generativity could also aid in promoting adaptive coping with the mental health stressors associated with climate change. Although empirical research on this specific topic is scarce, our argument builds off of well-established theoretical work on both the psychological nature of adaptive versus avoidant coping (e.g., Taylor & Stanton, 2007; Zeidner & Saklofske, 1996) and the role of hope and efficacy in promoting effective engagement with large-scale challenges (e.g., climate change).

Legacy Motivation, Generativity and Climate Action

Previous research has suggested that personal legacy can play a significant role in promoting proenvironmental action. For instance, work by Wade-Benzoni and colleagues found a prosocial effect of legacy motivation in intergenerational decision-making contexts (Fox et al., 2010; Wade-Benzoni, 2019; Wade-Benzoni & Tost, 2009). Other experimental work shows that making one's personal legacy salient increases how pro-environmentally people act in behavioral tasks/paradigms that assess proenvironmental behavior (Bang et al., 2017; Grolleau et al., 2021; Shrum, 2021; Syropoulos et al., 2023a; Syropoulos et al., 2023b; Wickersham et al., 2020; Zaval et al., 2015). Simply making one aware of their own mortality can increase concerns for one's personal legacy, which in turn promotes their generosity towards future generations in a climate change goods game (Hurlstone et al., 2020). These findings suggest that concerns for personal legacy could be a useful lever for encouraging pro-environmental action. It's worth noting, however, that this work stems mainly (if not exclusively) from online (web-based) studies, which limits both generalizability and applicability. Intervention work applying these methods of making one's legacy salient is required to test effectiveness in more ecologically valid settings.

Closely related work on generativity demonstrates a positive relationship with climate change engagement. Recent work, for example, reveals that generativity is associated with elevated environmental concern (Afridi et al., 2021; Pratt et al., 2013). People consider engagement in generative behaviors as an important part of their environmentalist identity (Alisat et al., 2014; Horwitz, 1996; Matsuba et al., 2012). Those who express greater generativity (via self-reports) also report greater pro-environmental attitudes (Jia et al., 2015; Jia et al., 2016; Milfont & Sibley, 2011; Wells et al., 2016) and engage in more sustainable purchasing behaviors (Giménez García-Conde et al., 2016; Shiel et al., 2020; Urien & Kilbourne, 2011).

The American Psychiatric Association (APA) encourages individuals to engage in climate mitigation and adaptation behavior, in an effort to both be better prepared to deal with the impacts of climate change and to respond to these impacts when they occur (see APA, 2023). The aforementioned evidence illustrates that being concerned about one's legacy or being asked to reflect on one's legacy motivates climate action. Thus, relying on existing evidence about the effectiveness of personal legacy (and the related construct of generativity) we theorize that people who think and act on their legacy more often would also be the ones who would be more likely to engage in climate mitigation and adaptation, helping them (and their family) be prepared to deal with the impacts of climate change. We also argue that this focus on leaving a legacy might have heretofore overlooked psychological benefits.

Legacy Motivation, Generativity and Mental Health

Whereas the connection between wanting to leave a legacy and environmental stewardship is both relatively straightforward and well-established in the empirical literature, it is perhaps less obvious how and why concern about one's legacy might be beneficially linked with mental health outcomes. After all, worrying about leaving a positive legacy could simply be yet another source of anxiety in one's life, especially in the face of so many interlocking, massive societal challenges—from climate change to global poverty to food and water shortages to the advent of super-powerful artificial intelligence—that seem to elide individual-level solutions.

Although such concerns are valid, we argue that engaging in legacy-building activities could potentially serve a protective, proactive function for people's mental health, especially in the context of large-scale, collective action problems such as climate change. In part, this builds from the very definition of the concept of legacy provided above (Wade-Benzoni, 2019): "an enduring meaning attached to one's identity and manifested in the impact that one has on others beyond the temporal constraints of the lifespan". In this definition, three things are made apparent: (1) meaning-making is an important activity that is attached to a person's identity which both motivates and helps them built their legacy; (2) wanting to leave a personal legacy focuses on positively impacting other people's lives, and (3) this positive impact lasts beyond the temporal constraints of the lifespan. Taken together, these three components of personal legacy suggest the following: first, personal legacy, through engagement in legacy-building activities, will help people find meaning; second, it will motivate them to engage in meaningful action (as highlighted in the previous section); and third, this action will help people form an enduring identity that could help them deal with existential threats (specific to their own mortality). Also important for this link between legacy motivation, well-being, and action is a sense of hope: without a belief that one can have an impact (i.e., that humanity can address climate change; that an individual can make a difference), such actions may be difficult to maintain. An individual who has developed this enduring sense of identity has likely also developed hope, through their belief that they will impact future others, which should then help them to remain engaged.

Each of the features of legacy motivation (i.e., sense of meaning, motivation for prosocial behavior, protection against existential threat) has direct implications for mental health and well-being. However, research on the association between personal legacy (and legacy motivation) and mental health is sparse. Only one study finds evidence that those who express greater concern for their legacy report feeling more grateful in their life (Syropoulos & Markowitz, 2021), which is an important predictor of mental health (Portocarrero et al., 2020). Aside from this work, there is no research that we know of which explicitly connects personal legacy and benefits to one's mental health.

However, our predictions can be informed by work focusing on generativity. Generativity and legacy motivation are constructs that overlap, as they both focus on attempts made to confer benefits to future generations of people (kin or not). Erikson, who coined the term generativity (Erikson, 1950) argued that at one point in our lives we have this desire to care for those who will come after us. Driven by this desire, we seek to pass values and teachings that will help them live better lives.

Given this overlap between legacy motivation and generativity, we can gain some initial insight into the potential mental health implications of legacy building efforts by exploring extant work on the relationship between generativity and mental health. A small but robust literature has explored this link. Generativity interventions (e.g., Gruenewald et al., 2016), for example, have been found to decrease psychological distress and even pro-inflammatory gene expression (e.g., Moieni et al., 2020). In research on older adults, those who felt more generative also exhibited lower mortality risk (Gruenewald et al., 2007, 2009; 2012). Correlational evidence suggests that adults who report greater

generativity also report greater psychosocial well-being, such as lower levels of depression, or greater feelings of self-efficacy and mastery (Grand et al., 1988; Gruenewald et al., 2007; 2009; McAdams et al., 1993). Aside from associations between generativity and fewer negative mental health consequences, evidence also links generativity to increased life satisfaction and self-reports of happiness (An & Cooney, 2006; Keyes & Ryff, 1998; Serrat et al., 2016). Generativity also helps individuals adjust to new roles in their lives, such as being a grandparent (Thiele & Whelan, 2008), or a retiree (Serrat et al., 2016).

Taken together, the above-referenced empirical and theoretical work strongly suggests that both legacy motives and generativity can serve as productive aides for coping with existential threat. While there is limited research on personal legacy and mental health, studies on generativity highlight a clear benefit to one's mental health which lends support to the proposed link between legacy and wellbeing. Further empirical work is needed, however, to fully explore this potential link.

Coping with Climate Change

People can and do use a variety of coping strategies—some more adaptive and proactive than others—when they feel stressed about climate change (Mah et al., 2020). For example, avoidant coping strategies—which involve distancing oneself or denying the existence or severity of a threat to alleviate psychological stress—may be prevalent amongst some individuals or groups in part because climate change is not a problem which can be resolved by the action of a single person. In contrast, more active coping strategies that work towards addressing the root problem—such as resolving to change one's behaviors to reduce one's own carbon emissions or taking time to prepare one's household for climate impacts (e.g., create a disaster kit for extreme weather)—are also reasonable and likely responses to the threat of climate change.

Adaptive Climate Change Coping Strategies

Adaptive coping refers to the use of coping strategies which promote well-being. Importantly, the strategies which are considered adaptive for any given individual will vary greatly depending on the stressor being dealt with and the resources individuals have at their disposal (Folkman & Moskowitz, 2004). While the adaptiveness of coping strategies depends on the context, coping with climate change should involve a combination of strategies that deal with the emotional aspects and those that involve mitigation and adaptation behaviors (Doherty & Clayton, 2011). Coping which involves thinking about or acting on one's legacy might be a way to achieve this potentially powerful and productive combination of coping strategies.

There is some research which supports the need for multiple kinds of coping. In addition to the kinds of proactive and problem-focused coping strategies people might use to protect their well-being in stressful situations, it is also important to engage in meaning-making coping strategies (Ojala, 2012a, 2012b; Park & Folkman, 1997). This meaning-making coping might involve altering one's perceptions of the stressor or one's responses to it by linking those perceptions and responses to important personal values. Such meaning-making coping strategies are needed in tandem with active coping strategies when dealing with a stressor that cannot be changed simply by individual behavior (e.g., climate change). Only using active coping strategies (i.e., strategies aimed at changing the source of stress) will result in action that is not sustainable; ultimately, the negative emotions that might have initially spurred the action will remain (Feather & Williams, 2022). We believe that personal legacy might be a way to make meaning of one's efforts to cope with climate change.

Benefits of Coping Through Meaning-making

Empirical work has examined the importance of coping via meaning-making. In studies of children and adolescents, Ojala (2012b) found that one way that they cope with their climate stress is by trying to seek out the positives, for example by believing that humanity will come together to address climate change and feeling a sense of trust towards leaders and scientists in their ability to find climate solutions. Research on the relationship between well-being and different coping strategies used for climate anxiety by children suggested that engaging in problem-focused coping strategies—such as doing what one can to help—has a positive association with greater reported negative affect, and with increased worry (Ojala, 2012a). However, there was some evidence that meaning-focused coping can buffer these negative effects: children who engaged in high levels of both problem- and meaning-focused coping reported less negative affect than those who reported low meaning- but high problem-focused coping (Ojala, 2012a).

Other work which examined the role of psychological (in)flexibility in the relationship between concern about climate change and distress (i.e., worry and engagement in the issue and climate change anxiety) also highlights the importance of meaning-making (Feather & Williams, 2022). In this work, the researchers hypothesized that greater psychological flexibility, which includes “identifying one’s values and taking committed action in line with those values” (p.139), might attenuate the impacts of being concerned about climate change and experiencing psychological distress. In parallel, they suggest that inflexibility, which includes “lack of contact with values and inaction” (p.139), might increase the likelihood of experiencing distress. They found support for the idea that inflexibility strengthens the relationship between climate change concern and distress (Feather & Williams, 2022). Although this work was cross-sectional, the findings suggest that decreasing psychological inflexibility may represent one way to ensure that proenvironmental engagement does not worsen mental health.

Legacy Motivation and its Potential Influence on Coping with Climate Change

While the research reviewed above does not directly measure legacy, other related work suggests that one’s values can be linked to coping strategies. For example, the measures used in Ojala’s work did not specifically measure thinking of one’s legacy as a meaning-focused strategy but did include a belief that despite the challenge climate change poses, we must have hope (Ojala, 2012a). Linking legacy to proenvironmental behaviors, i.e., focusing on the long-term and additive benefits of these behaviors, could be a useful way to promote hope and avoid the sense that one’s actions are insufficient or ineffective. Alternatively, when that sense of meaning is lacking, continuing to engage in proenvironmental behavior could feel like a futile exercise if no change in the stressor itself (i.e., climate change) is observed. People may feel helpless and give up efforts to cope. We might imagine that when people are able to accept their climate change emotions—and act on them in ways that align with their values, including their desire to leave a positive legacy—this could be a way to add meaning to and thus attenuate the potential for negative health impacts of engaging in proenvironmental behavior.

Further, as a psychological construct, legacy motivation is considered a psychological mechanism that helps individuals deal with existential threat (McAdams & Aubin, 1992; Wade-Benzoni & Tost, 2009), that is, one’s concerns about their mortality (see literature on Terror Management Theory, TMT; e.g., Greenberg et al., 1997). In fact, scholars have posited that TMT can provide novel insight into people’s emotional and behavioral responses to climate change (Smith et al., 2022), as it gives us a perspective of how individuals might react to a specific threat that makes their own mortality salient. Thus, personal legacy may serve as a valuable mechanism to increase engagement in climate action and build resilience in the face of climate change. Legacy can help individuals make sense of their own mortality and potentially cope with it through pro-social actions.

Without confronting and accepting the negative internal states they may be experiencing or finding ways to connect pro-environmental actions to important values, people who are concerned about the environment may experience burn-out and may not successfully cope with the psychological impacts of climate change (Feather & Williams, 2022). While climate change cannot be addressed by any one individual working in isolation from others, many individuals acting together can have a difference. To sustain that action, connecting those individual choices and behaviors to one's legacy might be a viable strategy.

Future Directions

The current investigation highlights how concerns for establishing personal legacy could be a powerful tool to motivate individual climate action, promote constructive and active coping with climate change stressors, and reduce the impact of climate change stressors on mental health. Establishing the associations theorized in this investigation could provide concrete empirical evidence for the positive impact of legacy for coping and well-being. To do so will require new empirical investigations on a number of related fronts.

Focusing on Youth and Young Adults

Because (climate change and proenvironmental) legacy building is a long-term activity that unfolds and evolves over time, longitudinal research is critical. This work should include diverse samples, with a particular focus on younger adults and adolescents. We know that younger generations tend to express greater worry for climate change (Coffey et al., 2021), yet much of the work on generativity focuses on older generations; moreover, the concept of legacy may be relatively less salient in everyday life for younger individuals. Thus, there is a clear need to examine these constructs in younger populations as well. Examining how and when legacy motives form and evolve in early adulthood, how they are expressed at various life stages, and how they affect behavioral and (mental) health outcomes will provide valuable insight into their utility from an intervention perspective. Further, the causal, and perhaps bidirectional, pathways between legacy, active coping, and well-being would be best explored through longitudinal work due to the long-term nature of these various constructs.

Need for Interventions Outside of the Lab

Intervention work is clearly called for in this domain. So far, work intended to promote and/or leverage legacy motivation has focused on intervention at a single time-point, with no evidence for the prolonged effectiveness of legacy interventions. These "single-touch" interventions which leverage legacy could prove useful for behaviors that happen infrequently but have lasting consequences (e.g., a large green purchase or commitment or green voting behavior). However, finding a way to frequently remind individuals of the legacy-building implications of their behaviors could prove particularly effective for sustaining day-to-day proenvironmental behavior and coping. Ecological momentary assessment designs could help us understand how often people think about their legacy. Daily or weekly diary designs could help us examine whether meaningful reflection on one's legacy can sustain the beneficial effects noted in online studies. Randomized control trials that are conducted in different communities could offer causal evidence for interventions that focus on targeting people's legacy. A multi-pronged approach that incorporates ecologically valid study designs is critical for pushing this topic of research forward.

Generalizability or Limitation of Legacy Interventions

Efforts that seek to pinpoint what behaviors and outcomes are most or least impacted by legacy-framing interventions are also worthwhile. Most research to date has focused on economic behaviors or donation tasks (e.g., Shrum, 2012; Zaval et al., 2015), which appears to be impacted by legacy interventions. However, it is not yet clear whether more diverse sets of climate-friendly actions are similarly amenable to change via legacy-based interventions. This becomes of paramount importance as not everyone has the same capacity to engage in climate action. We speculate that even mundane behaviors could be reframed as legacy-building activities. For example, turning off the lights or choosing to buy a green product might seem relatively inconsequential in the fight against global climate change. But, when reframed as part of one's legacy-building efforts, such behavior could be seen as more effective, helping individuals shift their anxiety stemming from climate towards action, while also promoting hope and active coping in day-to-day life. Thus, even for those with relatively limited capacity to engage in climate action, mundane behaviors could be reframed as legacy-building activities and thus be seen as meaningful actions. Moreover, actions that are less frequent, accessible to more people, and hold arguably more influence in promoting sustainability (e.g., voting for a specific pro-climate candidate; engaging in collective action), should also be studied as outcomes of intervention campaigns. Such work could highlight whether well-strategized and timely campaigns before key events (e.g., local and national elections) could also spearhead change.

Need for Consistent, Reliable and Valid Measures

Essential for all aforementioned study designs is the need to have reliable, valid and consistent measurement approaches for capturing legacy, generativity, hope, and coping with climate change. Although there has been no formal review on the measurement properties of legacy concern scales, the most frequently used measure is that used by Zaval and colleagues (2015). However, it is not clear whether this measure reflects a person's trait or state legacy concerns. Further, it is also not clear whether legacy is a unidimensional construct. In fact, evidence from work on people's values differentiates between altruistic and egoistic values (De Groot & Steg, 2009), which could suggest that people similarly may be motivated to leave a legacy for egoistic (caring about being remembered as someone with a good reputation) or prosocial (i.e., caring about their impact on others) reasons.

With regards to measures of coping, while general measures of coping exist (e.g., COPE, Carver & Scheier, 1994), researchers have also created ways of measuring climate-change-specific coping (e.g., Ojala & Bengtsson, 2019). While specific measures as well as qualitative methods of capturing specific coping strategies are useful for understanding what people do about climate change stress, they have disadvantages when it comes to comparing climate change coping to coping with other stressors. Further, there is no single measures of 'climate change coping' which has been widely validated or employed. Researchers should carefully consider what they want to understand about coping and its relations to other constructs to choose an appropriate measure.

Finally, future work should include measures of well-being, including hope. Some work has measured hope about climate change, noting the difference between hope based in denial and constructive hope (Ojala, 2012). While this measure has not been widely employed, it captures important nuances of hope about climate change which have different implications for well-being, which should be considered by anyone interested in hopefulness. There are also measures of hope used in the climate change domain which do not make the distinction between hope based in denial and constructive hope, see Swim & Fraser (2013); Geiger et al. (2019, 2021). Other measures of well-being, including eco-depression and eco-anxiety/climate change anxiety, have been developed and validation studies have found that these are distinct from general anxiety and depression (e.g., Clayton & Karazsia,

2020). Because of this, these more specific measures should be used when studying legacy and coping in this context.

Research on Different Aspects of Mental Health

Research into other related concepts and mental health in the climate change context is also needed. Although the existing research on the two related constructs of personal legacy and generativity was summarized, the review was limited in scope. Other future-oriented constructs could prove helpful and could also be considered as mechanisms that can increase all the aforementioned outcomes. Some of these include future-self continuity (how similar and close to one's future self a person feels; Hershfield & Bartels, 2018), consideration of future consequences (how much one considers the impact and consequences of their actions in the future; Strathman et al., 1994) and long-term orientation (having virtues and values that promote thinking about the future; e.g., Bearden et al., 2006). Examining their impact on well-being, coping and action in the climate change domain could thus prove useful.

Parenthood and Close Relationships

Studying personal legacy within the context of parenthood and other close relationships could also prove useful. A recent review (Shrum et al., 2023) finds that the evidence for the "green parenthood" effect is mixed. However, the same research suggests that future-oriented constructs that focus on impact on others (e.g., generativity and legacy) could be the reason why some positive effects are observed. Understanding how and when parents are motivated to act in ways that will benefit their children, and how they (and their families) can cope with climate change via legacy-building efforts is also important. Much of the work on climate change coping has focused on the mental health of children and youth (Clayton et al., 2023; Ojala, 2012, 2013). Studying family dynamics around climate change in the context of legacy might help us to better understand how to promote their well-being.

More broadly, investigations of the influence of different characteristics of close relationships on people's legacy and generativity might also prove useful in helping us understand how relationships influence coping with climate change and climate action. To the best of our knowledge, there is limited evidence on how relationship quality, satisfaction, conflict or support, as well as more dispositional traits such as a person's attachment style, influence how concerned people are about their legacy, or how generative they feel. Our predictions in this domain can be influenced by existing work which highlights gratitude (e.g., Algoe, 2012; Algoe et al., 2010) as an important part of high-quality close relationships. Since gratitude is a robust predictor of legacy (Syropoulos & Markowitz, 2021) and overall concern for future generations (Syropoulos et al., 2021), we could expect a similar pattern of results for legacy, such that those in environments with healthier relationships and more support also report more concerns for their legacy, and thus might be more likely to act proenvironmentally and cope constructively with climate change.

Hope and Climate Change

From a theoretical standpoint, we want to highlight the importance for more research on the concept of hope in the climate change domain (Geiger et al., 2021; Marlon et al., 2019; Ojala, 2023). As the impacts of climate change are experienced more frequently in daily life, feelings of hopelessness might become more prevalent. It could be the case that simply engaging in climate action does not translate into feeling hopeful for the future. It is also possible that hope on its own might not motivate individuals to engage in climate action in the first place. As the aforementioned findings suggest, personal legacy (and generativity) can both motivate action and benefit one's mental health. It is possible that when

framed as a legacy-building activity, climate action could generate hope, which in the long run could sustain proenvironmental engagement.

Conclusion

Climate change requires transformational changes to the ways we relate to one another and our planet, produce and consume resources, and live our lives, both as individuals and as a society. Yet transformational change in the face of existential threat is deeply challenging, in part because it is stressful and overwhelming to think about, and thus easy to turn away from. Recent research suggests, however, the helping people to develop strong commitments to building a positive legacy for ourselves, future generations and our planet could help support and promote more adaptive responses to the challenge.

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REFERENCES

- Afridi, S. A., Shahjehan, A., Haider, M., Gul, S., & Khan, W. (2021). Generativity and green purchase behavior: The role of environmental concern and pro-social attitudes. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 9(2), 344–357. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2021.9234>
- Algoe, S. B. (2012). Find, Remind, and Bind: The Functions of Gratitude in Everyday Relationships. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 6(6), 455-469. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9004.2012.00439.x>
- Algoe, S. B., Gable, S. L., & Maisel, N. C. (2010). It's the little things: Everyday gratitude as a booster shot for romantic relationships. *Personal Relationships*, 17(2), 217-233. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6811.2010.01273.x>
- Alisat, S., Norris, J. E., Pratt, M. W., Matsuba, M. K., & McAdams, D. P. (2014). Caring for the earth: Generativity as a mediator for the prediction of environmental narratives from identity among activists and nonactivists. *Identity*, 14(3), 177–194.
- American Psychiatric Association (2023). Resilience and Individual Actions Before and After a Disaster. Accessed via <https://www.psychiatry.org/patients-families/climate-change-and-mental-health-connections/resilience-and-individual-actions-before-and-after>
- An, J.S., & Cooney, T.M. (2006). Psychological well-being in mid to late life: The role of generativity development and parent-child relationships across the lifespan. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 30, 410–421. [doi:10.1177/0165025406071489](https://doi.org/10.1177/0165025406071489)
- Atske, S. (2022, August 31). Climate Change Remains Top Global Threat Across 19-Country Survey. Pew Research Center's Global Attitudes Project. <https://www.pewresearch.org/global/2022/08/31/climate-change-remains-top-global-threat-across-19-country-survey/>
- Bang, H. M., Koval, C. Z., & Wade-Benzoni, K. A. (2017). It's the thought that counts over time: The interplay of intent, outcome, stewardship, and legacy motivations in intergenerational reciprocity. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 73, 197–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2017.07.006>
- Bearden, W.O., Money, R.B. & Nevins, J.L. (2006). A measure of long-term orientation: Development and validation. *Journal of the Academy of*

- Marketing Science, 34, 456–467.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0092070306286706>
- Berry, H. L., Bowen, K., & Kjellstrom, T. (2010). Climate change and mental health: A causal pathways framework. *International Journal of Public Health*, 55(2), 123–132.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00038-009-0112-0>
- Brulle, R. J., Carmichael, J., & Jenkins, J. C. (2012). Shifting public opinion on climate change: An empirical assessment of factors influencing concern over climate change in the U.S., 2002–2010. *Climatic Change*, 114(2), 169–188.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-012-0403-y>
- Carver, C. S., & Scheier, M. F. (1994). Situational coping and coping dispositions in a stressful transaction. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 66(1), 184–195.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.66.1.184>
- Clayton, S. D., Pihkala, P., Wray, B., & Marks, E. (2023). Psychological and Emotional Responses to Climate Change among Young People Worldwide: Differences Associated with Gender, Age, and Country. *Sustainability*, 15(4), Article 4.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su15043540>
- Clayton, S., & Karazsia, B. T. (2020). Development and validation of a measure of climate change anxiety. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 69, 101434.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2020.101434>
- Coffey, Y., Bhullar, N., Durkin, J., Islam, M. S., & Usher, K. (2021). Understanding Eco-anxiety: A Systematic Scoping Review of Current Literature and Identified Knowledge Gaps. *The Journal of Climate Change and Health*, 3, 100047.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joclim.2021.100047>
- De Groot, J. I. M., & Steg, L. (2009). Mean or green: which values can promote stable pro-environmental behavior? *Conservation Letters*, 2(2), 61–66.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2009.00048.x>
- Doherty, T. J., & Clayton, S. (2011). The psychological impacts of global climate change. *American Psychologist*, 66(4), 265–276.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0023141>
- Doherty, T. J., & Clayton, S. (2011). The psychological impacts of global climate change. *American Psychologist*, 66(4), 265–276.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0023141>
- Erikson, E. H. (1950). *Childhood and society*. New York: Norton.
- Feather, G., & Williams, M. (2022). The moderating effects of psychological flexibility and psychological inflexibility on the relationship between climate concern and climate-related distress. *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science*, 23, 137–143.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcbs.2021.12.007>
- Flett, G. L. (2018). Mattering: Definitional considerations and historical advances. In *The Psychology of Mattering, Understanding the Human Need To Be Significant*, pp. 31–49.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-809415-0.00003-7>
- Folkman, S., & Moskowitz, J. T. (2004). Coping: Pitfalls and promise. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 55, 745–774.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.55.090902.141456>
- Fox, M., Tost, L. P., & Wade-Benzoni, K. A. (2010). The legacy motive: A catalyst for sustainable decision making in organizations. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 20(2), 153–185.
<https://doi.org/10.5840/beq201020214>
- Geiger, N., Gasper, K., Swim, J. K., & Fraser, J. (2019). Untangling the components of hope: Increasing pathways (not agency) explains the success of an intervention that increases educators' climate change discussions. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 101366.
[doi:10.1016/j.jenvp.2019.101366](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2019.101366)
- Geiger, N., Swim, J. K., Gasper, K., Fraser, J., & Flinner, K. (2021). How do I feel when I think about taking action? Hope and boredom, not anxiety and helplessness, predict intentions to take climate action. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 76, 101649.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2021.101649>
- Giménez García-Conde, M., Marín, L., & Ruiz de Maya, S. (2016). The role of generativity in the effects of corporate social responsibility on consumer behavior. *Sustainability*, 8(8), 815.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su8080815>
- Grand, A., Grosclaude, P., Bocquet, H., Pous, J., & Albarede, J.L. (1988). Predictive value of life events, psychosocial factors and self-rated health on disability in an elderly rural French population. *Social Science & Medicine*, 27(12), 1337–1342.
[doi:10.1016/0277-9536\(88\)90198-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536(88)90198-0)
- Greenberg, J., Solomon, S., & Pyszczynski, T. (1997). Terror management theory of self-esteem and cultural worldviews: Empirical assessments and conceptual refinements. In M. P. Zanna (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology*, 29, 61–

139. Academic Press.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(08\)60016-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(08)60016-7)
- Grolleau, G., Mzoughi, N., Napoléone, C., & Pellegrin, C. (2021). Does activating legacy concerns make farmers more likely to support conservation programmes? *Journal of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 10(2), 115–129.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/21606544.2020.1807410>
- Gruenewald TL, Karlamangla AS, Greendale GA, Singer BH, & Seeman TE (2007). Feelings of usefulness to others, disability, and mortality in older adults: The MacArthur study of successful aging. *The Journals of Gerontology Series B: Psychological Sciences and Social Sciences*, 62(1), P28–P37.
- Gruenewald TL, Karlamangla AS, Greendale GA, Singer BH, & Seeman TE (2009). Increased mortality risk in older adults with persistently low or declining feelings of usefulness to others. *Journal of Aging and Health*, 21(2), 398–425.
- Gruenewald TL, Liao DH, & Seeman TE (2012). Contributing to others, contributing to oneself: Perceptions of generativity and health in later life. *The Journals of Gerontology Series B: Psychological Sciences and Social Sciences*, 67(6), 660–665.
- Hershfield, H. E., & Bartels, D. M. (2018). The future self. In G. Oettingen, A. T. Sevincer, & P. Gollwitzer (Eds.), *The psychology of thinking about the future* (pp. 89–109). The Guilford Press.
- Horwitz, W. A. (1996). Developmental origins of environmental ethics: The life experiences of activists. *Ethics & Behavior*, 6(1), 29–53.
https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327019eb0601_3
- Hurlstone, M. J., Price, A., Wang, S., Leviston, Z., & Walker, I. (2020). Activating the legacy motive mitigates intergenerational discounting in the climate game. *Global Environmental Change*, 60, 102008.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2019.102008>
- Jia, F., Alisat, S., Soucie, K., & Pratt, M. (2015). Generative concern and environmentalism: A mixed methods longitudinal study of emerging and young adults. *Emerging Adulthood*, 3(5), 306–319.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2167696815578338>
- Jia, F., Soucie, K., Alisat, S., & Pratt, M. (2016). Sowing seeds for future generations. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 40(5), 466–470.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0165025415611260>
- Keyes CLM, & Ryff CD (1998). Generativity and adult lives: Social structural contours and quality of life consequences. In McAdams DP, & de St. Aubin E (Eds.), *Generativity and adult development: How and why we care for the next generation* (pp. 227–263). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- Latkin, C., Dayton, L., Scherkoske, M., Countess, K., & Thrul, J. (2022). What predicts climate change activism?: An examination of how depressive symptoms, climate change distress, and social norms are associated with climate change activism. *The Journal of Climate Change and Health*, 8, 100146.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joclim.2022.100146>
- Leiserowitz, A., Maibach, E., Rosenthal, S., Kotcher, J., Carman, J., Verner, M., Lee, S., Ballew, M., Uppalapati, S., Campbell, E., Myers, T., Goldberg, M., & Marlon, J. (2023). *Climate Change in the American Mind: Beliefs & Attitudes*, December 2022. Yale University and George Mason University. New Haven, CT: Yale Program on Climate Change Communication.
- Mah, A. Y. J., Chapman, D. A., Markowitz, E. M., & Lickel, B. (2020). Coping with climate change: Three insights for research, intervention, and communication to promote adaptive coping to climate change. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 75, 102282.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102282>
- Marlon, J. R., Bloodhart, B., Ballew, M. T., Rolfe-Redding, J., Roser-Renouf, C., Leiserowitz, A., & Maibach, E. (2019). How Hope and Doubt Affect Climate Change Mobilization. *Frontiers in Communication*, 4.
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fcomm.2019.00020>
- Matsuba, M. K., Pratt, M. W., Norris, J. E., Mohle, E., Alisat, S., & McAdams, D. P. (2012). Environmentalism as a context for expressing identity and generativity: Patterns among activists and uninvolved youth and midlife adults. *Journal of Personality*, 80(4), 1091–1115.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.2012.00765.x>
- McAdams, D. P., & Aubin, E. d. S. (1992). A theory of generativity and its assessment through self-report, behavioral acts, and narrative themes in autobiography. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 62(6), 1003–1015.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.62.6.1003>
- McAdams, D.P., de St Aubin, E., & Logan, R.L. (1993). Generativity among young, midlife, and older

- adults. *Psychology and Aging*, 8(2), 221–230. doi: 10.1037/0882-7974.8.2.221
- Milfont, T. L., & Sibley, C. G. (2011). Exploring the concept of environmental generativity. *International Journal of Hispanic Psychology*, 4(1), 21–30.
- Moieni M, Irwin MR, Seeman TE, Robles TF, Lieberman MD, Breen EC, Okimoto S, Lengacher C, Arevalo JMG, Olmstead R, Cole SW, Eisenberger NI. (2020). Feeling needed: Effects of a randomized generativity intervention on well-being and inflammation in older women. *Brain Behavior and Immunology*, 84, 97-105. doi:10.1016/j.bbi.2019.11.014.
- Ojala, M. (2012a). How do children cope with global climate change? Coping strategies, engagement, and well-being. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 32(3), 225–233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2012.02.004>
- Ojala, M. (2012b). Regulating Worry, Promoting Hope: How Do Children, Adolescents, and Young Adults Cope with Climate Change? *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, 7(4), 537–561.
- Ojala, M. (2013). Coping with Climate Change among Adolescents: Implications for Subjective Well-Being and Environmental Engagement. *Sustainability*, 5(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su5052191>
- Ojala, M. (2023). Hope and climate-change engagement from a psychological perspective. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 49, 101514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2022.101514>
- Park, C. L., & Folkman, S. (1997). Meaning in the context of stress and coping. *Review of General Psychology*, 1(2), 115–144. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.1.2.115>
- Portocarrero, F. F., Gonzalez, K., & Ekema-Agbaw, M. (2020). A meta-analytic review of the relationship between dispositional gratitude and well-being. *Personality and Individual Differences*. 164, 110101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2020.110101>
- Pratt, M. W., Norris, J. E., Alisat, S., & Bisson, E. (2013). Earth mothers (and fathers): Examining generativity and environmental concerns in adolescents and their parents. *Journal of Moral Education*, 42(1), 12–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057240.2012.714751>
- Serrat, R., Villar, F., Pratt, M.W., & Stukas, A.A. (2016). On the quality of adjustment to retirement: The longitudinal role of personality traits and generativity. *Journal of Personality*, 86, 435–449. doi:10.1111/jopy.12326
- Shiel, C., do Paço, A., & Alves, H. (2020). Generativity, sustainable development and green consumer behaviour. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 245, 118865. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118865>
- Shrum, T. R. (2021). The salience of future impacts and the willingness to pay for climate change mitigation: An experiment in intergenerational framing. *Climatic Change*, 165(1–2), 18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-021-03002-6>
- Shrum, T. R., Platt, N. S., Markowitz, E., & Syropoulos, S. (2023). a scoping review of the green parenthood effect on environmental and climate engagement. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, e818. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.818>
- Smith, L. K., Ross, H. C., Shouldice, S. A., Wolfe, S. E. (2022). Mortality management and climate action: A review and reference for using Terror Management Theory methods in interdisciplinary environmental research. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 13(4), e776. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.776>
- Stanley, S. K., Hogg, T. L., Leviston, Z., & Walker, I. (2021). From anger to action: Differential impacts of eco-anxiety, eco-depression, and eco-anger on climate action and wellbeing. *The Journal of Climate Change and Health*, 1, 100003. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joclim.2021.100003>
- Strathman, A., Gleicher, F., Boninger, D. S., & Edwards, C. S. (1994). The consideration of future consequences: Weighing immediate and distant outcomes of behavior. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 66(4), 742–752. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.66.4.742>
- Swim, J. K., & Fraser, J. (2013). Fostering Hope in Climate Change Educators. *Journal of Museum Education*, 38(3), 286–297. doi:10.1080/10598650.2013.11510
- Syropoulos, S., & Markowitz, E. M. (2021). Prosocial responses to COVID-19: Examining the role of gratitude, fairness and legacy motives. *Personality and Individual Differences*. 171, 110488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2020.110488>
- Syropoulos S., Markowitz, M., & Shrum, T. A. (2023a). letter to future generations: Examining the effectiveness of an intergenerational framing intervention. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*,

102074.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2023.102074>
- Syropoulos, S., Watkins, H., Goodwin, G. P., & Markowitz, E. (2023b). Disentangling the effects of impact-oriented versus reputation-focused legacy motives on intergenerational concern and action. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 90, 102092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2023.102092>
- Syropoulos, S., Watkins, H., Shariff, A., Hodges, S., & Markowitz, E. (2021). The role of gratitude in motivating intergenerational environmental stewardship. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 72, 101517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2020.101517>
- Taylor, S. E., & Stanton, A. L. (2007). Coping Resources, Coping Processes, and Mental Health. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, 3(1), 377–401. doi:10.1146/annurev.clinpsy.3.022
- The Global Risks Report 2022, 17th Edition. (2022). The World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/reports/global-risks-report-2022>
- Thiele, D.M., & Whelan, T.A. (2008). The relationship between grandparent satisfaction, meaning, and generativity. *International Journal of Aging and Human Development*, 66, 21–48. doi:10.2190/AG.66.1.b
- Urien, B., & Kilbourne, W. (2011). Generativity and self-enhancement values in eco-friendly behavioral intentions and environmentally responsible consumption behavior. *Psychology & Marketing*, 28(1), 69–90. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.20381>
- Wade-Benzoni, K. (2019). Legacy motivations & the psychology of intergenerational decisions. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 26, 19–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2018.03.013>
- Wade-Benzoni, K. A., & Tost, L. P. (2009). The egoism and altruism of intergenerational behavior. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 13(3), 165–193. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088868309339317>
- Wells, V. K., Taheri, B., Gregory-Smith, D., & Manika, D. (2016). The role of generativity and attitudes on employees home and workplace water and energy saving behaviours. *Tourism Management*, 56, 63–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2016.03.027>
- Wickersham, R. H., Zaval, L., Pachana, N. A., & Smyer, M. A. (2020). The impact of place and legacy framing on climate action: A lifespan approach. *PLoS One*, 15(2), e0228963. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0228963>
- Zaval, L., Markowitz, E. M., & Weber, E. U. (2015). How will I be remembered? Conserving the environment for the sake of One's legacy. *Psychological Science*, 26(2), 231–236. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797614561266>
- Zeidner, M., & Saklofske, D. (1996). Adaptive and maladaptive coping. In M. Zeidner & N. S. Endler (Eds.), *Handbook of coping: Theory, research, applications* (pp. 505–531). John Wiley & Sons.